

Usability of ‘The Networking Odyssey’ through Game-Based Learning for Networks Topic in Form Four Graph Theory

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Abstract- The study aims to develop and evaluate ‘The Networking Odyssey’, a game for teaching Networks in Graph Theory to Form Four students. It uses a Developmental Research Design (DRD) following the ADDIE Model, focusing on the game’s validity and usability. The Content Validity Index (CVI) obtained from three experts was 1, indicating excellent validity. A pilot study involving 15 students achieved a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.828, demonstrating strong reliability. Usability was evaluated using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), with the overall mean score of 3.52 out of 4, signifying high usability across four constructs. The game incorporates Game-Based Learning (GBL) to make STEM education more engaging by combining play and learning. It was found to increase students’ interest and understanding of Graph Theory effectively. Therefore, ‘The Networking Odyssey’ is a valid and useful educational tool that helps teachers improve students’ understanding of Networks in Graph Theory.

Keywords – Game, Network, Graph Theory, Form Four, Development

I. INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is one of the basic and main subjects that is often said to be challenging for students to master [1]. Not only that, Mamat & Wahab [1] also stated that a solid understanding of the basic concepts of Mathematics, as well as the ability to adapt applications over time, is a necessity that needs to be taken seriously. The subject of Mathematics is also one of the most important subjects in the education system in Malaysia [2]. The proof has been stated by Abu and Eu [2], who note that the Malaysian Ministry of Education (KPM) has implemented a new curriculum, the Kurikulum Standard Sekolah Menengah (KSSM), to enhance the national education system based on international benchmarks.

In this era of increasingly sophisticated technology, the use of technology in education can revolutionize and improve teachers’ teaching methods in this field [3]. In the same study, Kamaluddin & Husnin [3] also stated that the use of technology in Teaching and Learning sessions is encouraged to replace traditional teaching techniques. Since the country was hit by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has caused the government to implement the Movement Control Order (MCO), the use of technology in the field of education is increasing. As evidence by the report on the effectiveness of the implementation of Teaching and Learning at Home in 2020, most teachers have used an online approach when implementing their strategy of teaching [4].

Mathematics teachers need to improve their knowledge of various technologies to ensure that the Teaching and Learning sessions are more effective [5]. Therefore, one of the methods that can be used by teachers to ensure that the teaching sessions conducted are effective and efficient is to implement Game-Based Learning (GBL). This is so because the implementation of GBL is more effective compared to traditional learning [6]. Teachers need to apply the use of games in teaching, especially Mathematics teachers. Therefore, the use of ‘The Networking Odyssey’ is highly encouraged in Mathematics classes, especially for the topics of Networks in Graph Theory, so that the students’ interactions are more interesting and can have a positive impact on the students towards the topic. This can also indirectly increase the students’ level of understanding in the subject of Mathematics, as well as realize the

objectives that have been set in the Falsafah Pendidikan Kebangsaan (FPK).

GBL has gained traction in Malaysia's education system, particularly within 'Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics' (STEM) education, as a strategy to engage students and enhance their learning outcomes. GBL and STEM education are closely related as both focus on enhancing students' understanding and engagement. This is because GBL uses interactive games to teach STEM concepts in a more engaging and accessible way. This method not only improves students' academic performance in STEM subjects but also fosters critical thinking, creativity, problem-solving, and collaboration skills. Through GBL, students can explore complex STEM ideas in a fun, interactive environment that encourages experimentation and learning by doing. This can be supported through a study conducted by Min & Maat [7], who stated that the students learn mathematics voluntarily because the use of PBP has channelled students' fun and increased student motivation.

It is also one of the more creative and entertaining methods. Indirectly, students will pay attention to the teacher's lessons. This is because playing games is innate to the students [8], [9]. In other research by Ishak, Din & Hasran [10], it was also stated that the application of GBL makes the learners feel enjoyment while simultaneously enabling them to gain a better understanding of STEM content. In conclusion, integrating GBL into STEM education in Malaysia offers a dynamic approach to teaching that resonates with the digital-savvy nature of modern students. It bridges the gap between abstract concepts and practical application, making STEM subjects more engaging and accessible while equipping students with the skills needed for success in a technology-driven world.

Figure 1. Summary of 'The Networking Odyssey'

II. THEORETICAL-CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Ghazali & Sufean [11] have defined the conceptual framework as an overview through a diagram containing a flow chart. Not only that, Ghazali & Sufean [11] also stated that diagrams depict something symbolically and abstractly but can explain ideas related to the research being carried out. This study was conducted to develop a learning game platform or also known as Game-Based Learning, for the topic of Networks in Graph Theory, which is contained in KSSM Form Four. The model that has been used in this study is the ADDIE model, which is an acronym for five levels, namely; (i) Analysis, (ii) Design, (iii) Development, (iv) Implementation, and (v) Evaluation [12],[13]. The ADDIE model was chosen because this model is the main instructional design model and is often the source for other models to emerge.

Moreover, the concept of learning while playing, which is applied through Game-Based Learning (GBL), is an effort to attract students' interest in learning Mathematics, which is often considered a boring and complicated subject. Not only that, the development of the game, 'The Networking Odyssey', is designed to help students understand the topic of Networking in Graph Theory, which was newly introduced in KSSM. In addition, 'The Network Odyssey' was also developed to empower the use of technology in education, along with the passage of time. This topic was selected based on a literature review of previous studies.

The validity of 'The Networking Odyssey' needs to be examined to ensure that the game developed can achieve the objectives that have been set. The last process is to obtain the usability of 'The Networking Odyssey' which needs to be carried out among Form Four students from a secondary school in Shah Alam, Selangor to ensure that 'The Networking Odyssey' can be used and is compatible with the chosen topic and is easy to use among students in the school.

III. PREVIOUS RESEARCH

Game-Based Learning (GBL) for Mathematics subjects or mathematical games not only increases the effectiveness of learning, but it can also encourage students to learn without coercion [14]. Next, Marange & Adendorff [15] also shows that the use of teaching materials like the use of games in learning Mathematics is more effective than the traditional instruction model. Information and Communication Technology (ICT), such as GBL, needs to be applied during the teaching process, seen as one of the learning mediums that can involve students mastering Mathematics (Hammat, 2023). In addition, GBL also plays a role in more active participation among students during the learning session in progress [16].

In addition, GBL can also change students' perceptions or responses to learning as well as attract students' interest and motivation to follow the learning sessions conducted by the teachers [7]. In the same study, GBL also encourages a healthy competition system among students and develops their creativity. Next, in the study of Subramaniam & Maat [16], it was stated that Game-Based Learning (GBL) conducted in the classroom can improve understanding and learn a Mathematical concept through games. This is so because students will have the opportunity to learn through their experience and involvement in the game activity [16]. Research findings show that GBL can help students improve their mathematical skills and master these skills beyond traditional reading, writing, and counting skills [6]. Thus, it can be concluded that the developed 'The Networking Odyssey' is appropriate because the concept of GBL is applied in this game has a positive impact on students. Not only that, the use of technology in this game is also in line with the STEM goals for education in Malaysia.

Furthermore, the topic of Networks in Graph Theory is one of the fields of knowledge that needs to be studied in Mathematics, where the topic has various benefits in everyday life [17]. According to Awaris et al. [17], graphs are used to represent or model discrete objects (represented by points) and relationships between those objects (represented by edges). In the same writing, the map is also one example of the use of graphs in daily life, where if there is a road (side) that connects two different cities (points), then the two cities are interconnected. According to [18], a needs analysis was carried out on teachers who teach Form Four Mathematics in Pasir Mas district, Kelantan. The study has concluded that Mathematics teachers do not have teaching aids for the topic of Networks in Graph Theory. Not only that, but the analysis has also shown that the teachers are not exposed to other teaching aids except textbooks, as their level of readiness for using digital books is moderate [17]. The study of Milkova [19] also states that if interesting assignments are given for each topic, students will easily remember a topic that was studied better. Therefore, in the study, the researcher has used puzzles as teaching aids to help students understand graph-related problem solving. The use of the puzzle can attract students' interest and can increase imagination in students [19].

Additionally, in Eko's study [20] used a colouring set (Vertex colouring) and a dominance set (domination set) as teaching aids. The activity uses various materials such as whiteboard magnets, coloured magnets, balls, and small sticks to represent the vertices and the edges of the graph. This can give students a sense of fun to understand the concepts in Graph Theory [20]. Not only that, but the activity is also able to improve students' critical thinking skills [20]. Apart from the studies mentioned above, there is a newspaper clipping entitled "New Format of Mathematics Challenging the Minds of Students - Teachers" written by Ahmad, through the Berita Harian newspaper on June 21, 2023. Through the writing of the newspaper, it was stated that the format changed over the past three years, as well as the increasingly limited collection of questions, are among the causes of students in Mathematics subjects. This can conclude that the Network topic in Graph Theory is one of the topics that does not have a collection of questions like other topics in KBSM, because the topic is a new topic in KSSM.

IV. DESIGN AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study has been conducted based on a development study in a quantitative form. Development research is a design in developing modules, creating software, or building a model [11]. This study aims to develop an online game, 'The Networking Odyssey', in the topic of Networks in Graph Theory. Therefore, Developmental Research Design (DRD) and the ADDIE model have been applied in this development.

This study poses a main question: What are the appropriate characteristics to apply in 'The Networking Odyssey' regarding the topic of Networks in Graph Theory? Additionally, this study is accompanied by two specific questions as follows:

- i. Does 'The Networking Odyssey' have satisfactory validity?
- ii. Does 'The Networking Odyssey' have satisfactory usability?

V. METHDOLOGY

This study was first implemented by conducting a needs analysis and identifying the research problem. Next, the research objectives and research questions were also set to form an instrument to obtain the data related for this study. This study was conducted to develop a game which is named 'The Networking Odyssey' for the topic of Networks in Graph Theory found in KSSM Form Four Mathematics. The development is guided by the ADDIE model and applies the concept of learning while playing.

The next step for this study is to obtain findings and analyse surveys related to the development of ‘The Networking Odyssey’. In this section, two stages need to be carried out, namely, the first stage to obtain the validity, while the next stage is to obtain the usability of ‘The Networking Odyssey’. Based on the discussion with the supervising lecturer, three experts with more than 10 years of experience will be selected to carry out this study. This discussion is important to ensure that the chosen experts are suitable for the research being carried out. After the selection of experts is carried out, the findings will be analysed, and improvements will be implemented if necessary.

In the second stage, the usability stage of ‘The Network Odyssey’, the respondents who were chosen to answer the questionnaire were Form Four students at a national high school in Shah Alam. The school that was chosen has 12 classes for Form Four students. Respondents are selected by simple randomization, which is to ensure that the findings of the study can be evaluated from weak to high levels of mastery. In this section, the findings from each respondent will be collected and analysed descriptively.

Table -1 Summary of ADDIE model description

No.	Model Phase	Implementation
1	Analysis	Research requirements are analysed through reading previous studies related to GBL and Networks in Graph Theory.
2.	Design	The design of the study is evaluated and arranged based on the Form Four Mathematics DSKP as well as the reading of previous studies.
3.	Development	‘The Networking Odyssey’ was developed through a software named GDevelop.
4.	Implementation	A pilot study to obtain Cronbach’s Alpha values that have been set before the actual study is conducted.
5.	Evaluation	The actual study is conducted, and data is collected and analysed to make an evaluation.

Next, one of the research questions for this study is whether ‘The Networking Odyssey’ for the topic Networks in Graph Theory has satisfactory validity. The purpose of validity is to measure the accuracy of the measurement used in the study [21]. The instrument used to answer this question is the validation questionnaire, ‘The Networking Odyssey’, which was given to three selected experts. After obtaining the results, the data will be analysed using the Content Validity Index (CVI) value to determine the level of validity of the product produced [22]. According to Lynn [23], the CVI value should reach one if the number of experts selected is less than five people . Therefore, this study needs to reach a value of one to ensure that the game, ‘The Networking Odyssey’, has satisfactory validity because the number of experts used is three.

The next question for this study is whether ‘The Networking Odyssey’ for the topic Networks in Graph Theory has satisfactory usability. To answer this question, the instrument used is the usability survey form, ‘The Networking Odyssey’. The respondents involved were 50 Form Four students from a national high school located in Shah Alam, Selangor. Therefore, the research instruments used in this study are the validity questionnaire form, ‘The Networking Odyssey’, and the usability questionnaire form, ‘The Networking Odyssey’.

The validity questionnaire has 34 items that include face validity and content validity for the game ‘The Networking Odyssey’, the questionnaire instrument, and the user manual. Next, the usability questionnaire consists of four constructs, namely design, conceptual understanding, user convenience, and satisfaction. The data obtained for the validity questionnaire was analysed using the calculation of the Content Validity Index (CVI), while the data for the usability questionnaire was analysed descriptively using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software to identify the average value of the mean score through descriptive statistics for each construct.

5.1. ‘The Networking Odyssey’

‘The Networking Odyssey’ is a game that applies a play-while-learning approach to attract students' interest in learning the topic of Networks in Graph Theory. It can also indirectly help teachers in creating an active environment in the classroom and create an active environment in the classroom.

This game is about a student named Mark who is trapped in a mysterious village. Mark was asked by the village

chief to leave the village immediately. However, he needs to solve three multiple questions in seven different locations that Mark need to pass to get the secret map to get out from the mysterious village. Before going to the last location, the user must go through each location to answer three questions based on subtopics within this topic. The short quiz will start from the second location until the last location. The quiz given is related to the note that displayed before answering the quiz.

The first location is an introduction page to this game. While the last location is a challenging part because in this section, users need to make sure the chosen answer is the right one because the wrong answer will be leading to the first question of this part and the user will lose their lives as it only provided three chances. So, students should understand and master the Networks in Graph Theory topic in order to help Mark and his adventure in the mysterious village.

After successfully helping Mark out of the village, a display of the answers chosen throughout the game will be displayed. This is to help the teachers evaluate which questions need to be discussed together. Not only that, users can also enter their name in the space provided on the display page to determine their position on the leaderboard of this game.

VI. RESULTS

After the study is conducted and data is collected, data analysis was done to obtain the validity of ‘The Networking Odyssey’, the reliability of the instruments, and the usability of ‘The Networking Odyssey’ to determine whether this study can answer each of the questions that have been set. Thus, a more complete explanation related to the three findings will be explained in more detail in this section.

6.1. Validity of ‘The Networking Odyssey’

Expert validity in the study refers to the extent to which the results of the study can be accepted and acknowledged. Therefore, the validity of the game ‘The Networking Odyssey’ was measured through the calculation of CVI. CVI is measured by asking experts to rate each item in the study instrument. In this study, the calculated CVI value is divided into I-CVI and S-CVI. I-CVI refers to the value of each item that agreed or reached the relevant scale (scales 3 and 4).

divided by the total number of experts. Meanwhile, for S-CVI/Ave, that is the total amount of I-CVI divided by the number of items. Tables 2 shows the summary for the values of I-CVI and S-CVI obtained in this study for the three aspects involved after the instrument validity process for the game 'The Networking Odyssey' was implemented.

Table -2 Summary of the I-CVI and S-CVI obtained

Face & Content Validity	I-CVI	S-CVI/Ave
Game	1	1
Questionnaire	1	1
User Manual	1	1

Based on the data in the table above, the I-CVI value for each item is 1. According to Lynn [1823], the CVI value needs to reach a value of one if the number of experts selected is five and below. Based on the results of the study in the table above, it shows that this study has satisfactory validity because the CVI value that has been obtained is 1.

6.2. Reliability of the Instruments

Chua [24] stated that reliability refers to the ability of a study to obtain similar values when the same measurement is repeated. Research reliability is important because measurement errors can be reduced, and the relationship between items or variables can be measured accurately. To assess the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach's Alpha value was used through SPSS software. According to Daud et al. [25], a very good value for Cronbach's Alpha is between 0.80 to 1.00. In addition, this statement is also supported by Bond and Fox [26], which in the study stated that the best value for Cronbach's Alpha is between 0.80 to 1.00. Figure 2 below shows the interpretation scale for Cronbach's Alpha values from Bond and Fox [26].

Reliability Coefficient (α)	Item Reliability Level
0.80 – 1.00	Very good and effective with a high level of consistency
0.70 – 0.79	Good and acceptable
0.60 – 0.69	Acceptable
$\alpha < 0.59$	Item needs repair
$\alpha < 0.50$	Items need to be dropped

Source: Bond and Fox (2015)

Figure 2. Reliability value scale

To test the reliability of the instrument, a pilot study on 15 Form Four students was carried out at a national secondary school located in Shah Alam, Selangor. This is so because, according to Rahman, Ismail & Tan [27], the sample size of 15 people in a pilot study is sufficient. Next, the data obtained was analysed using SPSS software version 26.0. The following is Cronbach's Alpha value based on a pilot study for the usability questionnaire instrument of the game 'The Networking Odyssey'. Therefore, the reliability of the instruments for this study can be accepted because the value obtained is 0.828, which is very good and effective with a high level of consistency.

Table -3 Value of Cronbach's Alpha

Cronbach's Alpha	N of items
0.828	18

6.3. Usability of 'The Networking Odyssey'

The second question for this study is to determine whether 'The Networking Odyssey' has satisfactory usability. Therefore, the instrument that has been used to assess the objective is a usability. There are four constructs used in this instrument, namely the design construct and concept understanding construct, which have five items, as well as the user convenience construct and the satisfaction construct, which have four items.

In this study, the evaluation level table by Riduwan (2012) was used as a guide to determine the acceptance level based on the mean score value. Figure 3 below explains the level of acceptance based on the mean score value.

Mean Score Range	Mean Score Level
1.00 – 1.50	Less Related
1.51 – 2.50	Low
2.51 – 3.50	Modest
3.51 – 4.00	High

Source: Riduwan (2012)

Figure 3. Acceptance level based on mean score value

The results of the game usability questionnaire are shown as in Table 4. Four constructs have been evaluated, which are design, conceptual understanding, user convenience, and satisfaction. The analysis of these four constructs was carried out to identify the level of usability of the game ‘The Networking Odyssey’ for the topic Networks in Graph Theory. The mean score value for the constructs of design and conceptual understanding is 3.53 and 3.31, respectively. Meanwhile, the construct of user convenience and satisfaction has reached a high level, namely 3.61 and 3.60, respectively.

Table -4 Summary of study findings

Construct	Mean Score Value	Level
Design	3.53	High
Conceptual Understanding	3.31	Moderate
User Convenience	3.61	High
Satisfaction	3.60	High
Average Mean Score Value	3.52	High

The overall average of the mean score value of 3.52 has shown that the value is within a high level of usability, which is between 3.51 to 4.00. This shows that the game ‘The Networking Odyssey’ that has been developed has satisfactory usability.

VII. DISCUSSION

Based on the analysis that has been carried out, the following is a discussion related to the findings of this study. First, a total of three experts were selected and appointed to obtain validity to determine whether the first question can be answered or not. The three experts were selected based on their experience of more than 10 years in the field of education or Mathematics. The experts consist of two lecturers from the Department of Mathematics, UPSI, and a secondary school teacher from the field of Mathematics. Overall, the findings of the study have shown that the I-CVI value for each item for the three aspects is 1. Therefore, this result has proven that the game ‘The Networking Odyssey’ has satisfactory validity.

Next, a pilot study was conducted on Form Four students at a national high school located in Shah Alam, Selangor. The data analysis method using SPSS was used to obtain the Cronbach’s Alpha value. This is to see the extent the research instruments’ reliability is acceptable or not based on the findings. This study has a very good and effective instrument reliability with a high level of consistency, which is 0.828. This is supported according to the statement of Bond and Fox [26], which states that a value between 0.80 to 1.00 is the best value for Cronbach’s Alpha.

After that, the actual study was conducted face-to-face involving a sample of 50 Form Four students from the chosen national high school located in Shah Alam, Selangor. The data analysis method used to achieve this objective is descriptive statistics, which involves mean. The data obtained are analysed to ensure that the second research question in this study can be answered. Overall, the findings of the study show that the overall average for the mean score value for all four constructs, namely design, concept understanding, user convenience, and satisfaction for the game ‘The Networking Odyssey’ is high, which is 3.52. In conclusion, the results obtained have

proven that the game 'The Networking Odyssey', which has been developed based on the ADDIE model, is good and appropriate.

In 2013, the government, through the Ministry of Education (MOE), launched the Malaysia Education Blueprint, which outlines a phased implementation strategy consisting of three waves, beginning in 2013 and continuing until 2025. One of the key objectives is to strengthen the focus on science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) in schools across the country. This initiative aims to align with the nation's future workforce needs, particularly in response to the demands of the Fourth Industrial Revolution.

Game-based learning (GBL) has emerged as a powerful tool for enhancing STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education in Malaysia. The integration of GBL into the educational system is crucial in addressing the decline in student interest and achievement in STEM subjects, as well as in promoting 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and collaboration. In Malaysia, the Ministry of Education has recognized the potential of GBL in making STEM subjects more engaging and accessible to students.

Research shows that GBL can significantly improve students' motivation and academic performance in STEM by providing a fun and interactive learning environment [28]. In another study by Zubair et al. [29], it was stated that games are one of the most effective techniques in active learning and have been previously utilized in STEM education. Thus, it can be concluded that the game 'The Networking Odyssey' is one of the approaches that teachers need to use when teaching. Not only can the use of technology in the classroom be applied, but the use of this game can also attract students' interest in learning. So, this can indirectly help teachers in improving thinking skills and the level of mastery in students.

Therefore, the use of GBL, such as the game 'The Networking Odyssey', is very important in the field of education. This learning while playing activity can also help teachers in increasing student engagement and create an active environment during teaching and learning sessions. It can be proven through research from Zubair et al. [29], which states that efforts to incorporate innovative teaching methods, such as game-based learning in STEM education, have been shown to improve student engagement and learning outcomes.

However, this is not only important for the student's educational performance, but it can also help the student in the field of employment later. It is proven in a study that it is important for students to possess higher-order thinking skills to become more employable in the future [30].

VIII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this game not only has its innovation and creativity, but it can also help students understand the concepts in the topic of Networks in Graph Theory. In addition to being able to expand the level of student mastery, this creative and innovative game-based learning approach can also attract students to learn the topic of Networks in Graph Theory. Not only that, this game can also indirectly improve students' thinking skills as well as help students make connections between this topic and their daily lives. Therefore, this study is expected to be expanded to help students understand the topic of Networks in Graph Theory more easily and effectively.

Moreover, the use of this game in education is also one of the good alternatives to apply technology during teaching and learning sessions. The use of games in education is also important in creating active involvement from students. This is to ensure that the teaching and learning sessions conducted are two-way interactions between the teacher and students. This can indirectly help students in improving their mastery in topic of Networks in Graph Theory. In addition, the use of technology that uses various audio, visual, and animation can attract students' interest while the teacher is teaching in the classroom. Moreover, learning while playing can also prevent students from feeling bored and create a sense of fun in completing the tasks provided in the game.

Furthermore, the use of games in education can also strengthen teachers' skills in using technology while teaching and diversify their teaching methods so that students do not get bored and tired of old and traditional teaching methods, such as the use of whiteboards in the classroom. Finally, it is proven that the game 'The Networking Odyssey' has an important role in improving students' mastery and understanding of the topic of Networks in Graph Theory. This game can also show that its use can increase the use of technology in the country's education system.

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